

DEDNAED

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Project Acronym: DeDNAed

Deliverable 1.1
Report on the Kick-off Meeting

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Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
List of participants.....	4
Agenda of the Meeting.....	5
Abbreviations.....	7

Introduction

The DeDNAed Kick-off meeting took place virtually due to the ongoing SARS-COV-2 pandemic, on March 18th, 2021. The meeting allowed all partners of the consortium to get to know each other and to establish good relationships among them. After a short summary of the project idea and the objectives, the project officer Antonio Loredan presented some general information about the project and about the administrative and management procedures that will be followed during project execution (deliverables, reports) and gave some advices on good communication with the EU Commission. In the second part of the meeting, each work package was presented by its work package leader and the partners had fruitful discussions about the scientific work to be carried out in the project. Some details of the tasks could already be aligned between the partners. In the last part of the meeting, the nomination of the strategic management board took place. Julia Hann (TUC) was appointed as Project Manager, Florian Walch (BNN) as Dissemination Manager and Goran Bijelic (TEC) as Innovation and Exploitation Manager. All three nominations were made unanimously. After some open discussions about the project logo and the possibilities of the data sharing point, the meeting was closed with a virtual group photo (shown in fig. 1).

DeDNAed's kick-off meeting was the first step for a successful execution of this FET-Open project.

Fig. 1: Group photo of the virtual kick-off meeting.

List of participants

Name	Abbreviation	Institution
Julia Hann	JH	TUC
Andreas Morschhauser	AM	TUC
Danny Reuter	DR	TUC
Susanne Hartmann	SH	TUC
Particia Bartzel	PB	TUC
Aitziber L. Cortajarena	ALC	CICB
Laura Saa	LS	CICB
Andreas Heerwig	AH	KSI
Michael Mertig	MM	KSI
Frédéric Amiard	FA	UM
Aicha Azziz	AA	UM
Marc Lamy de la Chapelle	MLC	UM
Mathieu Edely	ME	UM
Wafa Safar	WS	UM
Saloni Agarwal	SA	UP
Frank Bier	FB	UP
Adriana Wipperling	AW	UP
Nerea Briz	NB	TEC
Javier Lou	JL	TEC
Verónica Mora	VM	TEC
Goran Bijelic	GB	TEC
Nikolaus Ladenhauf	NL	BNN
Susanne Resch	SR	BNN
Florian Walch	FW	BNN
Antonio Loredan	AL	EU Commission

Agenda of the Meeting

Time	Topic	Speaker
9:00 – 9:05 AM	Welcome message by the Coordinator	Danny Reuter, Julia Hann
9:05 – 9:20 AM	Overview of the DeDNAed project: Objectives, Concept, Methodology and Ambition	Julia Hann
9:20 – 10:10	Introduction talk of the PO	Antonio LOREDAN
10:10 – 11:30 AM	Introduction of the Partners of Consortium (10 min-long presentations) : roles in the project, facilities/skills/know-how relevant for the project, introduction of any staff, their roles and tasks, contact points, 2 min for questions)	
10:05 AM	TUC	Danny Reuter
10:15 AM	CICB	Aitziber L. Cortajarena
10:25 AM	KSI	Michael Mertig
10:35 – 10:50 AM	Coffee break	All
10:50 AM	UM	Marc Lamy de la Chapelle
11:00 AM	UP	Frank Bier
11:10 AM	TEC	Nerea Briz
11:20 AM	BNN	Nikolaus Ladenhauf
11:30 AM – 2:40 PM	Goals for WP presentations : Plan & actions, critical issues like Deliverables or Milestones for the next 6 months	WP-leaders
11:30 AM	WP2: Design and Production of Sensing element	CICB Aitziber L. Cortajarena
11:50 AM	WP3: Design and synthesis DNA origami	KSI Michael Mertig
12:10 – 12:50 PM	Lunch	All
12:50 AM	WP4: Synthesis & characterization of DNA origami hybrids	KSI/UM Michael Mertig / Marc Lamy de la Chapelle
1:10 pm	WP5: Integration of DNA origami	TUC Julia Hann
1:30 pm	WP6: Validation against state-of-the-art	UP Frank Bier
1:45	WP7: Transfer to flexible substrates and bio-safety	TUC Julia Hann / Frank Bier

2.00 pm	WP8: Dissemination, exploitation	BNN Nikolaus Ladenhauf
2:18 pm – 2:30 pm	Coffee break	All
2.30 PM	Project management (WP1)	TUC Julia Hann
	Management Structure and bodies	
	Strategic Management Board nomination and presentation	
	Procedures and tools	
	Financial aspects	
2:54 pm	Strategic Management Board Nomination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Manager • Dissemination Manager • Innovation & Exploitation Manager 	TUC Danny Reuter
2.58 PM	Open Discussion and Summary	Danny Reuter/ Julia Hann
	Project logo	All
	Data sharing point	All
3.40 PM - 3.50 PM	Closing remarks and greetings	Danny Reuter, All

Abbreviations

TUC	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET CHEMNITZ
CICB	ASOCIACION CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN BIOMATERIALES- CIC biomaGUNE
KSI	KURT-SCHWABE-INSTITUT FUR MESS- UND SENSORTECHNIK MEINSBERG EV
UM	UNIVERSITE DU MANS
UP	UNIVERSITAET POTSDAM
TEC	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION
BNN	BIONANONET FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH